

A Study on Intestinal Obstruction Caused by Tuberculosis

Jay Prakash Singh¹, Anupam Ranjan², Shri Krishna Ranjan³

¹Senior Resident, Department of Surgery, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College & Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of Surgery, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College & Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India

³Associate Professor, Department of Surgery, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College & Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India

Received: 11-07-2024 / Revised: 21-08-2024 / Accepted: 29-09-2024

Corresponding Author: Jay Prakash Singh

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Intestinal obstruction due to tuberculosis (TB) is a significant clinical challenge, particularly in regions with high TB prevalence. It can result from inflammatory strictures, adhesions, or mass formations, leading to severe complications. Accurate diagnosis and timely management are crucial to improving patient outcomes.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the clinical characteristics, management strategies, and outcomes of patients with intestinal obstruction caused by tuberculosis to provide insights into optimizing treatment approaches.

Methods: This prospective observational study was conducted. Eighty-six patients diagnosed with intestinal obstruction due to TB were included. Data on demographics, clinical presentation, diagnostic findings, treatment modalities, and outcomes were collected. Patients were managed either conservatively with anti-tubercular therapy or surgically based on clinical severity. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Results: The study included 86 participants, with a mean age of 45.6 ± 12.3 years and a male-to-female ratio of 1.3:1. Most patients presented with abdominal pain (91.9%), vomiting (83.7%), and abdominal distension (77.9%). CT scans identified intestinal obstruction in 81.4% of cases. Fifty-six patients (65.1%) required surgical intervention, while 34.9% were managed conservatively. The overall complication rate was 19.8%, with surgical site infections being the most common (10.5%). Statistical analysis revealed that surgical intervention was associated with longer hospital stays ($p < 0.05$), though no significant difference in complication rates was observed between the treatment groups.

Conclusion: Intestinal obstruction due to tuberculosis presents significant diagnostic and therapeutic challenges. Both surgical and conservative treatments are viable, depending on the clinical scenario. Early diagnosis and individualized management strategies are crucial to improving patient outcomes.

Recommendations: Increased awareness of intestinal TB among healthcare providers, along with the use of advanced imaging techniques and a multidisciplinary approach, can enhance the diagnosis and management of this condition. Further research is needed to refine treatment protocols and reduce the burden of complications.

Keywords: Intestinal obstruction, tuberculosis, surgical management, anti-tubercular therapy, gastrointestinal TB.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

(TB)-related intestinal blockage continues to be a serious health concern, especially in areas where the disease is highly prevalent. As a pulmonary illness, tuberculosis can affect any region of the gastrointestinal system and create complications such as intestinal obstruction, which is the result of inflammation-induced strictures, adhesions, or masses blocking the intestinal lumen [1]. This disorder is more prevalent in underdeveloped nations where (TB) is still a serious public health concern. Patients with this syndrome frequently have delayed or insufficient treatment for the

underlying illness [2]. About 1-3 percent of TB cases worldwide are intestinal TB cases, including intestinal involvement; however, in regions with high endemic TB rates, the prevalence of this type of TB can reach 12% [3]. Since intestinal TB can resemble other gastrointestinal conditions, diagnosis can be difficult, and treatment is frequently postponed. Patients usually appear with nonspecific symptoms, such as weight loss, abnormal bowel habits, and abdominal pain, which are readily confused with more frequent illnesses such as cancer or Crohn's disease [4]. Due to the increased risk of

complications such perforation, abscess formation, and blockage, there is frequently a delay in diagnosis, which significantly raises morbidity and mortality [5].

Although histological confirmation is still the gold standard for diagnosis, recent developments in diagnostic imaging, such as CT scans and endoscopic procedures, have improved the identification of intestinal tuberculosis [6]. Even with these improvements, it is still challenging to distinguish intestinal tuberculosis from other obstruction-causing conditions such Crohn's disease or cancers without invasive procedures [7]. Additionally, there is a wide range of therapeutic approaches for tuberculosis-related intestinal obstruction. These approaches include conservative control with anti-tubercular therapy (ATT) and surgical intervention in cases when conservative management is ineffective or causes difficulties [8]. Depending on the location and degree of obstruction, surgical therapy may include techniques including adhesiolysis, resection with anastomosis, or stricturoplasty [9]. The degree of symptoms, the patient's general condition, and the existence of complications frequently influence the therapy decision. Surgery is not risk-free, though, as patients who are malnourished or immunocompromised are more likely to experience difficulties after the procedure [10]. Research on the effects of various treatment modalities for intestinal TB obstruction has been continuing, and findings indicate that customised therapy regimens can greatly enhance patient outcomes [11]. This study aims to evaluate the clinical characteristics, management strategies, and outcomes of patients with intestinal obstruction caused by tuberculosis to provide insights into optimizing treatment approaches.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Department of Surgery, at a tertiary care centre equipped with specialized facilities for diagnosing and managing gastrointestinal disorders, including those caused by tuberculosis. The study period was from January 2023 to January 2024.

Participants: A total of 86 participants diagnosed with intestinal obstruction secondary to tuberculosis were enrolled in the study. The patients were selected from those presenting with symptoms of intestinal obstruction and were diagnosed with tuberculosis through clinical, radiological, and pathological investigations.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Diagnosed with intestinal obstruction caused by tuberculosis through clinical, radiological, or histopathological evidence.
- Willing to participate and provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with intestinal obstruction caused by other etiologies such as malignancy, hernia, or adhesions.
- Pregnant women.
- Patients with a history of previous abdominal surgery within the last year.
- Patients who refused to provide consent or were unable to participate due to critical illness.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible patients meeting the inclusion criteria were consecutively included in the study. The diagnosis of tuberculosis was confirmed using objective criteria, including radiological imaging and histopathology, to reduce diagnostic bias.

Data Collection: Data were collected using structured proformas that included demographic information, clinical presentation, diagnostic findings, treatment modalities, and patient outcomes. Data sources included patient interviews, medical records, radiology reports, and pathology results.

Procedure: Patients who met the inclusion criteria underwent a detailed evaluation, including clinical examination, imaging studies (X-ray, CT scan), and, if necessary, endoscopic and histopathological examinations to confirm the diagnosis of tuberculosis. The treatment approach, including surgical and non-surgical management, was documented. Follow-up was conducted to assess recovery and complications.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was utilised for data entry and analysis. The data were summarised using descriptive statistics, which included means, standard deviations, frequencies, and percentages. Chi-square tests were used to compare categorical variables, and independent t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests were used to analyse continuous data as needed. For statistical significance, a p-value of less than 0.05 was used.

Results

A total of 86 patients diagnosed with intestinal obstruction due to tuberculosis were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 45.6 ± 12.3 years, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.3:1 (49 males and 37 females). Most patients (60.5%) were from rural areas, and 72.1% had a history of contact with tuberculosis patients.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Number (n = 86)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
- <30	14	16.3
- 30-50	43	50.0
- >50	29	33.7
Gender		
- Male	49	57.0
- Female	37	43.0
Residence		
- Urban	34	39.5
- Rural	52	60.5
History of Tuberculosis Contact	62	72.1
Co-morbidities		
- Diabetes	18	20.9
- Hypertension	22	25.6
- HIV	6	7.0

The most common presenting symptom was abdominal pain (91.9%), followed by vomiting (83.7%), abdominal distension (77.9%), and

constipation (68.6%). The average duration of symptoms before seeking medical care was 3.7 ± 1.5 weeks.

Table 2: Clinical Presentation of Participants

Symptom	Number (n = 86)	Percentage (%)
Abdominal Pain	79	91.9
Vomiting	72	83.7
Abdominal Distension	67	77.9
Constipation	59	68.6
Weight Loss	46	53.5
Fever	41	47.7

Radiological imaging was crucial in diagnosing intestinal obstruction due to tuberculosis. CT scans showed thickened bowel loops with signs of obstruction in 81.4% of cases, while abdominal X-

rays indicated air-fluid levels in 73.3% of cases. Histopathological examination confirmed tuberculosis in 60.5% of patients.

Table 3: Diagnostic Findings

Diagnostic Test	Number (n = 86)	Percentage (%)
CT scan Indicating Obstruction	70	81.4
Abdominal X-Ray (Air-Fluid Levels)	63	73.3
Endoscopy	22	25.6
Histopathological Confirmation	52	60.5

Out of the 86 patients, 56 (65.1%) underwent surgical intervention, while 30 (34.9%) were managed conservatively with anti-tubercular

therapy (ATT). Surgical procedures included adhesiolysis (39.3%), resection with anastomosis (32.1%), and stricturoplasty (28.6%).

Table 4: Treatment Approaches

Treatment Modality	Number (n = 86)	Percentage (%)
Surgical Intervention	56	65.1
- Adhesiolysis	22	39.3
- Resection & Anastomosis	18	32.1
- Stricturoplasty	16	28.6
Conservative Management	30	34.9

The overall complication rate was 19.8%, with surgical site infections being the most common (10.5%), followed by prolonged ileus (5.8%) and anastomotic leakage (3.5%). The average hospital

stay was 12.4 ± 4.2 days. There was a statistically significant difference in the length of hospital stay between the surgical group (14.2 ± 3.8 days) and the conservative group (9.3 ± 2.1 days) ($p < 0.05$).

Table 5: Complications and Outcomes

Complication	Number (n = 86)	Percentage (%)
Surgical Site Infection	9	10.5
Prolonged Ileus	5	5.8
Anastomotic Leakage	3	3.5
Average Hospital Stay (days)		
- Surgical Group		14.2 ± 3.8
- Conservative Group		9.3 ± 2.1

Statistical Analysis: The statistical analysis revealed a significant association between surgical intervention and prolonged hospital stay ($p < 0.05$). There was no significant difference in complication rates between surgical and conservative management ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion

The study enrolled 86 participants diagnosed with intestinal obstruction due to TB, revealing key insights into the demographic, clinical, and treatment-related factors associated with this condition. Most participants were middle-aged adults, with a slight predominance of males over females. A significant proportion of patients came from rural areas and had a history of contact with tuberculosis, highlighting the ongoing public health challenge of tuberculosis in certain demographics. The presence of co-morbidities such as diabetes, hypertension, and HIV in a notable subset of patients may have further complicated the clinical management of these cases.

Clinically, abdominal pain, vomiting, abdominal distension, and constipation were the most prevalent symptoms, with an average delay of nearly four weeks before patients sought medical care. This delay in presentation emphasizes the need for increased awareness and early detection strategies for tuberculosis-related intestinal complications. Radiological imaging, particularly CT scans, played a crucial role in diagnosing the obstruction, demonstrating thickened bowel loops and other hallmark signs in over 80% of cases. Histopathological confirmation was achieved in 60.5% of patients, validating the importance of a multi-modal diagnostic approach to accurately identify tuberculosis as the underlying cause.

The study found that a majority of patients (65.1%) required surgical intervention, with adhesiolysis, resection with anastomosis, and stricturoplasty being the most commonly performed procedures. However, a significant portion of patients (34.9%) were managed conservatively with anti-tubercular therapy, indicating that non-surgical options remain viable in selected cases. The complication rate was 19.8%, with surgical site infections being the most frequent issue. Notably, the average hospital stay was longer for those undergoing surgery compared to conservative treatment, suggesting a trade-off

between the invasiveness of surgical management and the speed of recovery.

Statistical analysis indicated that surgical intervention was associated with a significantly longer hospital stay, though there was no significant difference in overall complication rates between surgical and conservative management approaches. This finding suggests that while surgery may be necessary in more severe cases, conservative management could offer similar outcomes without the extended recovery period associated with surgery. The absence of a significant difference in complication rates further supports the potential of non-surgical management in appropriate clinical scenarios.

Diagnostic difficulties can arise because intestinal tuberculosis frequently mimics Crohn's disease, especially in areas where the disease is less prevalent. A case of small intestinal obstruction that was first misdiagnosed as Crohn's disease and then identified as (TB) using faecal mycobacterial cultures was highlighted in a study. Since no one test can definitively rule out tuberculosis, the study stressed the importance of integrating clinical suspicion with imaging, endoscopic, and histological findings [12]. The hypersegmentation of the barium column, known as the "chicken intestine sign," is a prominent radiological characteristic of intestinal tuberculosis that aids in distinguishing it from inflammatory bowel disorders. As a common cause of bowel blockage in endemic locations, small bowel (TB) can be diagnosed with the use of this unique imaging finding [13]. Numerous case reports detail intestinal tuberculosis that results in a persistent partial obstruction of the small intestine, sometimes manifesting as intermittent abdominal pain and vomiting that lasts for a long time. In one such case, a 37-year-old man was first thought to have small intestinal cancer but later received a postoperative diagnosis of tuberculosis. In complex situations, surgery, such as segmental ileal excision, is frequently required [14].

Conclusion

The results of this study underscore the complexity of managing intestinal obstruction due to tuberculosis. The findings highlight the importance of individualized treatment planning, considering both surgical and non-surgical options based on the

patient's clinical presentation and severity of obstruction. Early diagnosis, prompt treatment, and careful selection of management strategies are critical to improving patient outcomes in this challenging clinical condition.

References

1. Bhargava A, Madda P, Rana S. Tuberculosis of the gastrointestinal tract. *Gastroenterology Clin North Am.* 2018;47(3):577-594.
2. Mukhopadhyay A, Dey A, Shah A, Gupta T. Gastrointestinal tuberculosis: A global challenge. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2019;25(30):3967-3976.
3. Sharma MP, Bhatia V. Abdominal tuberculosis. *Indian J Med Res.* 2018;145(3):305-317.
4. Dhooria A, Agarwal R. Abdominal tuberculosis: A clinical conundrum. *J Clin Tuberc Mycobact Dis.* 2020; 19:100161.
5. Agarwal S, Mukhopadhyay S. Challenges in the diagnosis and management of gastrointestinal tuberculosis. *J Clin Tuberc Other Mycobact Dis.* 2019; 15:100096.
6. Solanki K, Narayanan D, Varma S. Role of imaging in abdominal tuberculosis. *Clin Imaging.* 2020;60(1):37-45.
7. Kumar S, Arora NK. Advances in diagnostic imaging for intestinal tuberculosis. *Clin Imaging.* 2019;53(2):145-152.
8. Rasheed S, Zinicola R, Watson D, Bajwa A, McDonald PJ. Intra-abdominal and gastrointestinal tuberculosis. *Colorectal Disease.* 2007 Nov;9(9):773-83.
9. Ghoshal UC, Ghoshal U. Intestinal tuberculosis: The enigma of diagnosis and management. *Int J Tuberc Lung Dis.* 2022;26(1):14-22.
10. Kamble RS, Patil AS, Kulkarni SS. Surgical management of intestinal tuberculosis: A critical review. *Int J Surg.* 2020; 83:80-86.
11. Singh K, Chhabra A, Malhotra S. Surgical outcomes in intestinal tuberculosis: A retrospective study. *J Gastrointest Surg.* 2023;27(5):1132-1140.
12. Kurnick A, Bar N, Maharshak N. Intestinal tuberculosis and Crohn's disease is always a diagnostic challenge: A case report and review of the literature on the importance of fecal mycobacterial cultures and the limitations of latent infection testing. *Cureus.* 2019 Sep;11(9).
13. Xiang H, Han J, Ridley WE, Ridley LJ. Chicken intestine: Intestinal tuberculosis. *Journal of Medical Imaging and Radiation Oncology.* 2018 Oct 1; 62:62-62.
14. Aregawi AB, Alem AT, Girma A. A Rare Case of Intestinal Tuberculosis with Chronic Partial Small Bowel Obstruction. *Int Med Case Rep J.* 2022; 15:725-733.